

Pylephlebitis Associated with a Liver Abscess in Diverticulosis: A Case Report

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Abstract

Pylephlebitis is a rare but serious condition characterized by septic thrombosis of the portal vein, usually secondary to intra-abdominal infections such as diverticulitis. We report the case of a 63-year-old man who presented with diffuse abdominal pain, fever, nausea, and vomiting evolving over 20 days. Laboratory tests revealed leukocytosis, elevated inflammatory markers, and hepatic cytolysis. Abdominal computed tomography showed a hepatic abscess associated with portal vein thrombosis extending to the splenic vein, in the setting of colonic diverticulosis without signs of diverticulitis. The patient was treated with intravenous antibiotics and anticoagulation, with favorable clinical and radiological evolution. Pylephlebitis should be considered in patients presenting with signs of infection and portal vein thrombosis. Early diagnosis and prompt treatment are essential to improve outcomes.

Introduction

Pylephlebitis, or septic thrombosis of the portal vein, is an infectious suppurative thrombosis of the portal vein and/or its intrahepatic branches. This diagnosis is extremely rare and is a complication of abdominal infections, particularly diverticulitis. [1]

It can lead to serious complications such as liver abscess, sepsis, peritonitis, and intestinal ischemia, worsening the prognosis.

We present here a case of suppurative thrombophlebitis of the portal vein trunk, associated with a liver abscess on a diverticular colon without signs of diverticulitis.

Case Presentation

A 63-year-old man presented to the emergency department with diffuse abdominal pain, most pronounced in the hypogastric region and around left iliac fossa, which had been developing over the previous 20 days. He also reported nausea and early postprandial vomiting, all occurring in the context of feverishness and episodes of chills.

The patient had no particular medical history other than smoking 45 pack-years, and no personal or family history of hypercoagulability, thrombosis, or cancer.

More Information

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On admission, the patient was hemodynamically and respiratorily stable, with a fever of 38.1°C. Examination revealed only slight tenderness in the right upper quadrant and hypogastric region, with no guarding or contracture. There was no hepatomegaly or jaundice. Laboratory findings revealed leukocytosis of 14,850/mm³ with marked neutrophilia (11,880/mm³) and a C-reactive protein (CRP) level of 347 mg/L. Cytolysis was observed, with aspartate aminotransferase (AST) at 103 IU/L and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) at 112 IU/L. There was no anemia or thrombocytopenia, and bilirubin levels were within normal limits.

Abdominal-pelvic computed tomography showed a poorly defined collection in segments VI and VII of the liver measuring 84x74x46mm, with evidence of hypodense material opposite the portal bifurcation and at the level of the portal trunk extending to the splenic terminus, which are partially opacified at this level, on a diverticular sigmoid and descending colon.

The diagnosis was pylephlebitis associated with a hepatic abscess on colonic diverticulosis without signs of diverticulitis.

A conservative therapeutic approach with intravenous antibiotics and anticoagulation was adopted. The patient was started on subcutaneous anticoagulation every 12 hours for portal vein thrombosis, along with intravenous metronidazole 500 mg every eight hours combined with ceftriaxone 2 g per day for the treatment of pylephlebitis.

The patient showed clinical improvement under antibiotic therapy and anticoagulation. He no longer experienced abdominal pain, fever, or vomiting after ten days of hospitalization.

A follow-up abdominal ultrasound showed a reduction in the size of the collections with a normal-sized portal vein that was patent on Doppler.

Discussion

Pylephlebitis is a suppurative thrombophlebitis of the portal vein or its branches, secondary to an intra-abdominal or pelvic infectious focus or intra-abdominal inflammation leading to thrombosis.

Most cases involving liver abscesses also include a contiguous intra-abdominal infection such as diverticulitis or pancreatitis [2-3].

The portal system is a venous network responsible for venous drainage from the digestive tract, spleen, pancreas, and gallbladder to the liver. The portal vein is formed by the confluence of the superior mesenteric vein and the splenic vein, usually behind the neck of the pancreas. It divides at the hepatic hilum into right and left portal branches, which penetrate the hepatic parenchyma to provide portal perfusion of the hepatic lobes. The mesenteric veins drain the small intestine and colon, respectively, including the sigmoid colon, a common site of diverticulosis. In the event of intra-abdominal infection, particularly diverticular infection, septic thrombophlebitis can spread along the mesenteric venous branches to the portal vein, causing pylephlebitis. This hematogenous spread can lead to the formation of secondary liver abscesses due to septic portal emboli.

Figure 1: Anatomy of the Hepatic Portal Vein System and Its Tributaries

Source: [12]

Hepatic abscess is one of the most difficult differential diagnoses, but in such cases it is difficult to establish causality. Was the primary process a liver abscess with secondary complications of pylephlebitis, or vice versa? Clinically, pylephlebitis can manifest as fever, chills, abdominal pain, nausea, jaundice, and abdominal tenderness. In two reviews, one of 19 cases and the other of 67 cases, fever was found in 100% and 87% of cases, respectively [3].

Elevated alkaline phosphatase (ALP) was observed in most patients, particularly those with contiguous pyogenic liver abscesses [5], and elevated blood markers of inflammation, bilirubin, or transaminase may be found.

The radiological diagnosis of choice is based on CT scan, as it is most likely to reveal a contiguous source of infection.

In the early stages of pylephlebitis, intravascular air is frequently observed, followed by the presence of thrombus a few days later [6]. The entire portal venous system may be affected. Two studies have been conducted in this regard. The first found that the portal vein was the most common site of thrombosis, while the second favored the right intrahepatic branch [7].

Signs indirectly suggestive of thrombosis include vein dilation [8], perivascular inflammation, and/or lymphadenopathy.

A check-up is recommended on day 5 or even day 7 of antibiotic therapy to identify the extent of the thrombus or any other complications [9].

Early broad-spectrum antibiotic treatment, regardless of the presence of bacteremia, is essential for at least 6 weeks. Oral medication can be administered once clinical and biological improvement is required. The antibiotic treatment of choice includes therapy targeting Gram-positive, Gram-negative, and anaerobic bacteria.

There is no uniform recommendation regarding the use of anticoagulation. A study by Kanellopoulou analyzing 100 cases of pylephlebitis found that patients receiving anticoagulant therapy had a more favorable outcome than patients treated with antibiotics alone [10].

Anticoagulation reduces the risk of chronic portal vein thrombosis and the resulting portal hypertension, and also prevents the formation of liver abscesses by reducing septic embolization to the liver from infected thrombi [11].

Conclusion

Pylephlebitis is a rare condition secondary to a common intra-abdominal infection, such as diverticulitis or appendicitis. It should be considered in patients presenting with an infectious syndrome and signs of portal vein thrombosis on imaging tests.

Early antibiotic therapy is necessary given the high mortality rate. The use of anticoagulants in pylephlebitis remains controversial.

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